

ROOTLINKS

Enabling primary producers to
thrive in the bioeconomy

R O O T L I N K S

THE CONTEXT

Why action is needed

Our Challenge

Primary producers (PPs) are the backbone of Europe's bioeconomy. However, they have yet to fully benefit from innovations and new value chains.

To change this, we must **remove the barriers they face** and create fair, sustainable opportunities for farmers, foresters, and blue economy operators in the circular bioeconomy.

What holds PPs back

LOW AWARENESS AND LIMITED COMMUNICATION

PPs are often not well informed or involved in bioeconomy innovation, which makes new opportunities harder to grasp.

WEAK INTEGRATION IN VALUE CHAINS

Many PPs struggle to connect and profit from circular bio-based markets, facing financial constraints, technological risks, and uneven benefits.

STRUCTURAL AND REGULATORY BARRIERS

Small farm size, rural isolation, ageing communities, and complex rules make participation in innovation more difficult.

THE SOLUTION

The RootLinks project

About RootLinks

RootLinks is a project funded by the **European Union** and supported by the **Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU)**.

It connects and empowers PPs through the **Working Group on Primary Producers (WGPP)**, bringing together representatives from **agriculture, forestry, and the blue economy**.

Agriculture

Blue Economy

Forestry

Governance

Guided by an **inclusive** governance model and **co-creative processes**, the WGPP works with RootLinks to develop a shared **Action Plan** that reflects PPs' priorities.

Approach

By combining **horizontal and sector-specific actions** across **five dimensions**, our approach makes the Action Plan both **practical and relevant**.

Actions

SECTOR-SPECIFIC ACTIONS

Addressing the needs of each sector

Activities focusing on the specific needs of agriculture, forestry, and the blue economy. They tackle **sector-specific challenges, provide tailored solutions, and enable producers** in each sector to fully participate in and benefit from circular bio-based value chains.

HORIZONTAL ACTIONS

Creating frameworks for collaboration

RootLinks supports the WGPP by setting up its structure to ensure smooth operations, developing a stakeholder engagement strategy with **formats to foster inclusion, and strengthening networking across sectors and regions.**

Objectives

We support the co-creation and implementation of an Action Plan with two main goals

1

OPEN OPPORTUNITIES

Promote **awareness** and enable PPs to benefit from **opportunities** generated by bio-based innovations, supported by sustainable and practical **business models**.

2

STRENGTHEN ENGAGEMENT

Empower PPs to play an **active and rewarding role** in CBE JU projects and in circular bio-based systems and value chains, while reinforcing their skills in **networking and collaboration**.

SECTORIAL GROUPS

Putting RootLinks into practice

AGRIMAKERS

Beyond food production, agriculture plays a crucial role in the bioeconomy by supplying biomass for a diverse range of bio-based products.

The **Agrimakers** involve **farmers, cooperatives, producer organisations, agri-food SMEs** and **rural advisors**.

Together, they co-develop strategies to:

- Increase **innovation uptake**
- Improve **value chain sustainability**

AQUANAUTS

The **blue economy** embraces a wide range of marine industries such as **seafood processing, shipbuilding, and ports.**

The **Aquanauts** bring together **fishers, aquaculture and algae farmers** as key actors.

The group contributes to:

- **Ensuring food security, trade and jobs**
- **Sustainable innovation and circular growth.**

FORESTERS

The **Foresters** include all actors supplying products while protecting ecological balance and supporting rural livelihoods. They are **forest owners, loggers, arborists, engineers, researchers, and educators.**

RootLinks supports them by

- Fostering awareness, cooperation, and capacity building
- Helping forestry actors engage in sustainable bio-based value chains.

JOINING ROOTLINKS

Why primary producers should take part

Opportunities

VISIBILITY AND INFLUENCE

Stronger voice in shaping Europe's bioeconomy and position in value chains.

FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES

Improved access to funding opportunities and new markets.

PRACTICAL TOOLS AND TRAINING

Knowledge, methods, and support to turn ideas into action.

NEW PARTNERSHIPS

Connections with industry, policymakers, and other producers across Europe.

CONTRIBUTION TO POLICY

Improved practices that help deliver the EU Green Deal, support the Widening Strategy and ERA, and contribute to the UNSDGs.

Become a member: WGPP

If you want to play an active and rewarding role in circular bio-based value chains, contribute to shaping EU funding priorities and solutions, and access new opportunities for cooperation, capacity building, and innovation uptake, then the WGPP is for you.

Who can join?

- Primary producers with a legal entity
- Cooperatives or producer organisations
- Associations, networks, or advisory services working with primary producers

APPLY:

- [Visit the dedicated page on the CBEJU Website](#)
- [Fill in the Application Form](#)

FOR QUERIES:

- primary.producers@cbe.europa.eu
- info@rootlinks.eu

What to expect from WGPP and what not

- Active engagement & representation
- Collaboration & knowledge sharing
- Deliver outputs & follow through

- Passive observation
- Execution of CSA tasks
- Pure service providing

OUR TIMELINE

Follow the progress

Timeline

4/2025
KICK-OFF

**Creation of
Action Plan**
9/2025

6/2025
**WGPP Warsaw
Meeting**

**Start implementation
of the Action Plan**
4/2026

4/2028
**Uptake of the Action
Plan by WGPP...**

3/2029
**...and beyond
the WGPP**

IMPACTS

Benefits for society and the environment

IMPACTS OF THE PROJECT

IMPACTS OF THE PROJECT

IMPACTS OF THE PROJECT

IMPACTS OF THE PROJECT

THE TEAM

Consortium and contacts

RootLinks Partners

ICONS

VISIT OUR WEBSITE
ROOTLINKS.EU

FOLLOW US ON
SOCIAL MEDIA

CONTACT US
INFO@ROOTLINKS.EU

R O O T L I N K S

The logo consists of the word "ROOTLINKS" in a white, spaced-out, sans-serif font. Below the letters, there are four overlapping, curved lines in light blue, pink, yellow, and light blue, connecting the letters to form a stylized shape.

THANK YOU
FOR YOUR ATTENTION!